

**EVALUATION OF GENETIC VARIATION OF POTATO (*SOLANUM TUBEROSUM* L.)
ACCORDING TO AGROBIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS**

Hajiyev E.,

*PhD on Biological Sciences, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Immunogenetics,
Genetic Resources Institute, Ministry of Science and Education, Baku, Azerbaijan*

Mammadova A.,

*Doctor of Biological Sciences, Associate Professor, Chief Researcher of the Department of Physiological
Genetics of Plants, Genetic Resources Institute, Ministry of Science and Education, Baku, Azerbaijan*

Allahverdiyev E.,

PhD on Agrarian Sciences, Director of Research Institute of Vegetable growing, Baku, Azerbaijan

Hajiyeva S.,

*Researcher of the Department of Molecular Genetics and Genomics, Genetic Resources Institute,
Ministry of Science and Education, Baku, Azerbaijan*

Karimova A.,

*Researcher of the Department of Immunogenetics, Genetic Resources Institute,
Ministry of Science and Education, Baku, Azerbaijan*

Shirinova A.,

*Junior Researcher, Department of Technical and Forage Crops, Genetic Resources Institute, Ministry of
Science and Education, Baku, Azerbaijan*

Aliyev R.

*Doctor of Biological Sciences, Professor, Head of the Department of Plant Physiological Genetics, Genetic
Resources Institute, Ministry of Science and Education, Baku, Azerbaijan*

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Abstract

Due to the fact that potatoes are a valuable food product, an important technical and fodder crop, the study of this agricultural crop is of great importance for the country's economy. The purpose of this study was to study potato collection material to identify high-yielding varieties. 50 local and introduced potato genotypes were used in the. During the study, indicators such as average plant yield, average weight, amount of dry matter nitrates, sugar and extractives in tubers were studied. When assessing genotypes, correlation analysis showed that there is a very significant correlation between the average plant yield and the average weight of tubers ($r = 0.593$), between the dry matter weight and the presence of nitrates ($r = 0.448$), as well as between the content of sugar and extractives ($r = 0.696$). Of the 50 samples studied, the highest yield results were obtained for varieties numbered 10, 11, 15, 29, 30 and 49. It was noted that most samples with higher yields were characterized by a red color of the peel. The analysis of biochemical indicators showed a higher content of sugar, nitrates, extractive substances and mass of dry matter in highly productive genotypes compared to less productive samples. Highly productive genotypes are recommended for use in selection.

Keywords: potatoes, yield indicators.

INTRODUCTION

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* – $2n=48$), – a species of perennial tuberous herbaceous plants of the genus *Solanum* of the *Solanaceae* family. From a consumer point of view, potatoes are a vegetable. This is the oldest crop on the globe, which has been grown in the Andes of South America for more than eight thousand years.

Potatoes were first brought to Europe by the Spaniards in the second half of the 16th century. Subsequently, the cultivation of this crop spread everywhere [2] due to its significant nutrient content, productivity and ability to thrive in a variety of climates [4]. Today, potato is grown on more than 20 million hectares in 150 countries, with a total world production of about 360 million tons [3]. Currently, the presence of more than 160 types of potatoes has been proven.

In Azerbaijan, potato growing is developed in the western regions - Gadabay, Tovuz, Shamkir, partly in Dashkesan, Goygol, and also Gusar. One of the most important features of potato growing is the lack of

knowledge of the agrobiological properties of modern varieties. Increasing potato production is possible only with a comprehensive differential, systematic approach to solving the problem, taking into account the zonal factor, the level of development of production and scientific and technological progress, organizational, economic and social conditions.

When studying potatoes, you should pay attention to yield. The mass of potato tubers is of great importance for the formation of the crop [1]. It is extremely important to study the chemical composition of potato tubers [5].

Taking into account the above, the purpose of this study was to study collection material to identify high-yielding varieties, as well as to analyze some biochemical indicators of potato tubers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

50 local and introduced potato genotypes were used in the study (table 1). Morphobiological and biochemical evaluation was carried out on 5 randomly selected stem tubers of each sample. During the study,

indicators such as average plant yield (ISAPY), average tuber weight (ATW), nitrates, dry matter (DM), sugar and extractives were (EW) studied. The specified signs

were evaluated on the basis of an international descriptor.

Table 1.

Potato genotypes involved in the study

No	CODE	Name	No	CODE	Name
1	SF1	Agata	26	SF26	Murlie
2	SF2	Agila	27	SF27	Murovdaq
3	SF3	Agilo	28	SF28	Neptun
4	SF4	Alious	29	SF29	Olivea-A
5	SF5	Allergiya	30	SF30	Oqonyok
6	SF6	Anna Karella	31	SF31	Orkestr
7	SF7	Anna Iona	32	SF32	Qelebe
8	SF8	Anna Ş.	33	SF33	Qretola
9	SF9	Aranda	34	SF34	Sarishin
10	SF10	Arinda	35	SF35	Sarqunmira
11	SF11	Arizona A.	36	SF36	Sartala
12	SF12	Arizona B-clas	37	SF37	Sevinch
13	SF13	Berhina B-c	38	SF38	Silvina
14	SF14	Carrera	39	SF39	Sipropetu
15	SF15	Dzhlibel	40	SF40	Sirvina
16	SF16	Colombo	41	SF41	Slavyanka
17	SF17	Amiri	42	SF42	Sloretta
18	SF18	Fabula	43	SF43	Soraya
19	SF19	Gedabay	44	SF44	Shovgi
20	SF20	Impola	45	SF45	Suipatte
21	SF21	Kamal	46	SF46	Telman
22	SF22	Larise	47	SF47	Turan
23	SF23	Manague	48	SF48	Uqur
24	SF24	Manaque	49	SF49	Uniko
25	SF25	Marotona	50	SF50	Vaqif

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the mean values, standard deviation (SD), standard error (SE) and coefficient of variation (CV%) of the studied traits of potato genotypes.

Among the studied signs, the highest coefficient of variation was observed for the yield of the plant (CV=44%), and the lowest – for the mass of dry matter

(CV=9.1%). In our research, tuber mass (CV=42%) and nitrate accumulation (CV=34%) were identified as indicators with moderate variability. Of the studied signs, the coefficient of variation of the amount of sugar was extremely low (CV=15%), the range of variation of which was 2.9.

Table 2.

Statistical indicators of studied signs of potato genotypes

	SE	SD	CV	Diapazon	Minimum	Maksimum
ISAPY	28,93	204,6	44	815	186	1001
ATW	8,45	59,7	42	320	55	375
Nitrates	7,76	54,9	34	347,4	75,6	423
DM	0,27	1,9	9,1	7,1	18,3	25,4
Sugar	0,07	0,55	15	2,9	2,4	5,3
EW	0,09	0,70	17	3,31	2,75	6,06

Correlation analysis. Variability was calculated between two signs (table 3)..When assessing genotypes, correlation analysis can provide valuable information about the most important traits. By identifying traits that show significant correlation, the advantage of one trait over another can be predicted, and this can facilitate the selection of suitable genotypes. Some of the signs studied by us showed

such a significant interdependence that they should be taken into account in selection programs. It was noted that there is a very significant correlation between the average plant yield and the average weight of tubers ($r = 0.593$), between the dry matter weight and the presence of nitrates ($r = 0.448$), as well as between the content of sugars and extractives ($r = 0.696$).

Table 3.

Correlation between the traits of the studied potato genotypes

	ATW	Nitrates	DM	Sugar	EW
ISAPY	0.593**	0,135	0,029	-0,089	-0,052
ATW	1	-0,086	-0,248	-0,131	-0,215
Nitrat		1	0.448**	-0,171	0,18
DM			1	0,011	0,218
Sugar				1	0.696**

Cluster analysis. Cluster analysis was built according to the Euclidean index of genetic distance of the UPGMA package of statistical programs PAST. Genotypes for the studied characteristics were grouped into 2 main clusters (fig. 1).

The first cluster of dendrograms combined 34 genotypes of potato. It can be seen from the dendrogram that genotypes included in this cluster have medium and low indicators of the studied signs. In these samples, the ISAPY indicator varies between 186-498 grams. ATW indicators vary among genotypes in the range of 55-245 grams. Genotypes grouped by

nitrate indicators also had low and medium values. Although the majority of genotypes, grouped by the presence of dry matter, have minimum and average indicators, some samples are characterized by a higher value. Indicators of genotypes grouped by sugar content had minimal, medium and high values.

16 potato genotypes are grouped in the second cluster of the dendrogram. Genotypes, grouped in this cluster, have high indicators according to the investigated traits. Thus, the index of ISAPY in these plants fluctuates within 627-1001 grams, indicators of ATW – within 110-375 grams.

Figure 1. Dendrogram of the studied traits of potato genotypes

Genotypes grouped by the presence of nitrates were also characterized by medium and high values of this characteristic. Most of the genotypes, grouped by the content of dry matter, had a medium and high index. Indicators of genotypes, grouped by the amount of sugar, had average indicators.

Since the yield of the varieties depends on the growing conditions, one of the main conditions for increasing potato yields is the selection and planting of zoned varieties, taking into account local conditions. Obtaining high-quality and high-yielding potatoes depends on the combination of healthy seeds of the correct physiological age, a suitable seed bed and careful planting.

Thus, taking into account the fact that one of the conditions for increasing the yield of varieties are growing conditions, in particular, the selection and planting of zoned varieties taking into account local conditions, we conducted research in this direction in compliance with all necessary requirements. When studying the average yield of one plant and the average weight of one potato tuber, samples were identified (No. 5, 8, 10, 11, 14, 15, 16, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 35, 40, 49, 50), characterized by high productivity. Of the 50 samples studied, the highest yield results were obtained for varieties numbered 10, 11, 15, 29, 30 and 49. It was noted that most samples with higher yields were characterized by a red color of the peel. Analysis

of biochemical parameters showed a higher content of sugar, nitrates, extractives and dry matter mass in highly productive genotypes compared to less productive samples.

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